

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN PERIODONTAL DISEASE AND SOMATIC CELL DISEASE

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Annotation: Evidence of the relationship between the oral state and the general health of patients is constantly updated with new data. In recent years, people have become more and more interested in studying the two-way relationship between periodontal tissue diseases and various somatic diseases and conditions. This article provides a review of the data on this issue, provides evidence of the relationship between chronic oral infections and cardiovascular, endocrine system, rheumatoid arthritis and other somatic cellular diseases.

Keywords: periodontal disease, interrelationships, somatic pathology

Introduction: The evidence of the relationship between oral status and the general health of patients is constantly updated with new data (Doffer C., 2017; Kane S.F., 2017, R.H.Strait, 2021). A student of Koch, Miller V., author of the basic work "Microorganisms in the Mouth" V.D. For the first time, the concept of the influence of focal dental infection on the development of human and systemic diseases was proposed. Improved laboratory diagnosis, complex molecular and biological methods have enabled researchers to return to the role of oral infections as a trigger for the development of systemic diseases in the 1980s and 1990s, and continue to this day. The causal relationship between diseases is a complex concept, because any disease is caused by various causes and developmental mechanisms. In recent years, interest in studying the two-way relationship between periodontal (periodontal) tissue diseases and various somatic diseases and conditions has increased. The inflammatory process in periodontal tissue is determined by the

levels of pro-inflammatory and anti-inflammatory cytokines, mediated by free radical oxidation and immunologically unbalanced systemic responses. The activation of the host immune response caused by microorganisms and their metabolites stimulates the synthesis and release of cytokines, pro-inflammatory mediators, and matrix metalloproteinases, which leads to tissue destruction. These mechanisms explain the process of interaction between dental diseases and systemic diseases in the body. Scientist Rose L., Genco R.J. The term "periodontal disease medicine" was proposed to denote the periodontology part of the study of the effects of periodontal disease on the overall health of the body. Many researchers have reported increased endothelial dysfunction and systemic inflammation in patients with periodontal tissue disease, which provides a potential link between oral health and cardiovascular disease (Amar S., et al., 2003; Higashi Y., et al., 2008).

In the scientific literature, special attention is paid to the relationship between periodontal disease and cardiovascular and endocrine system diseases, rheumatoid arthritis and women's physical health. This publication provides summary data on the relationship between periodontal disease and somatic cell pathology. The pathology of the cardiovascular system and the periodontal disease mortality rate of cardiovascular disease largely determine the negative phenomena of the medical population situation in all countries. The etiological and pathological mechanism of the relationship between cardiovascular pathology and periodontal disease is discussed in the scientific literature. According to Stelzel M. And Sattler A. [71], The model of the pathological development of the cardiovascular system is as follows: bacteria localized in plaques and periodontal pockets secrete endotoxins and exotoxins. Periodontal pathogenic pathogens can also infect the endothelial cells of coronary arteries, which can promote platelet aggregation. It seems possible that anti-inflammatory cytokines, for example, released during the inflammatory response, may affect the course of coronary heart disease (CHD).

Mattila K.J.et al. The correlation between the main parameters of dental health, cholesterol and triglyceride levels and the frequency of coronary heart disease was established [55]. Proponents of the "inflammation hypothesis" point out that the inflammatory process in periodontal tissue contributes to the increase of C-reactive protein (CRP) and fibrinogen (PH) in the blood, and is a risk factor for the development of atherosclerosis and coronary heart disease. In fowler E.B., Breault L.G., Cuenin M.F. Differences in CRP levels in patients with periodontal disease and healthy people were also found in the study. (2001), and the CRP level of patients with severe periodontal disease was significantly higher than that of patients with mild pathology. Scientists Radafshar, Shad, Mirfeizi (2006), who established the difference in CRP levels in patients with myocardial infarction and periodontal disease and the myocardial infarction group without periodontal pathology, explained the increased risk of coronary heart disease prothrombotic state. Some authors suggest that this indicator be determined by a highly sensitive method (hsCRP) and consider a threshold level of hsCRP equal to 3mg/L. The risk of atherosclerotic complications was proactively determined by the inactive, slow inflammation detected by HCRP levels. Meurman J.H.et al. It was found that the CRP and PH in the serum of patients with cardiovascular pathology were significantly higher than that of the control group. Scientists have proven the relationship between poor sanitation and increased risk of cardiovascular disease. The relationship between cardiovascular disease and periodontal disease by Mattila K.J.confirm. And co-author, Muller H.P., Kolltveit K.M., Eriksen, they compared the results of the patient's dental examination (the number of teeth removed, the presence and depth of periodontal pockets, the loss of tooth attachment, the absorption of bone structure) with the number of their common disease processes Tar I.And Bagyi K.Chronic inflammatory processes in the apical region and periodontal tissue were found in 83% of patients with cardiovascular disease. A large number of scientific studies have been devoted to the study of periodontal

disease as an independent risk factor for the development of atherosclerosis and coronary heart disease.

The data obtained by NHANES (2015-2016 questionnaire analysis) provide evidence of the relationship between cardiovascular system diseases, as well as individual indicators (cholesterol, hypertension, angina pectoris) and periodontal pathology. Diabetes and periodontal disease often occur in the context of the pathology of the cardiovascular system in the context of diabetes, which is also a problem for the population of all countries: it is predicted that the number of people with diabetes will reach 228 million in 2025.

The impact of diabetes on many disease processes is one of the most concentrated development issues. Scientist Papapanou P.N. In his research, he proved that the severity of periodontal disease depends on the existence and severity of diabetes. It has been determined that diabetics have a higher risk of periodontal disease. Ftratlu et al. The level of hygiene of diabetics is similar to that of gingivitis, and the degree of alveolar attachment is higher. Although diabetes increases the risk of periodontal disease, there is evidence that periodontal tissue infection has a negative impact on diabetic blood sugar control. Taylor G. And co-author. In the case of significant changes in periodontal tissue, patients with type 2 diabetes have found violations of blood glucose control. Al-Mubarak S. And co-author's research. It includes assessing the condition of periodontal tissue and the general condition of patients with endocrine pathology (diabetes). It turns out that 6 and 12 weeks after treatment (removal of tooth deposits and antibacterial flushing), all indicators of the patient's teeth and general condition (improvement of blood glucose control) have a positive trend. Risk assessment is an integral part of the diagnosis and treatment of periodontal disease. It is clear that patients with concomitant systemic diseases (for example, diabetes mellitus) have a much higher risk of development and severity of periodontitis. Therefore, the periodontal disease prediction model includes a history of diabetes as a risk factor, as well as the possibility of controlling

blood sugar. The same serious problem as metabolic syndrome and periodontal disease is metabolic syndrome. According to experts from the World Health Organization, metabolic syndrome is considered a " pandemic of the XXI century."Metabolic syndrome is determined by the grouping of several interrelated risk factors (abdominal obesity, dyslipidemia, hyperglycemia, hypertension). Recent studies have revealed a positive correlation between periodontal disease and metabolic syndrome. Patients with the presence of three or four components of the metabolic syndrome have a more severe periodontal disease process. In daiotou F.In co-author's research. For patients over 45 years of age, the correlation between metabolic syndrome and severe periodontal disease was obtained (there are at least two sites with a missing alveolar attachment-6 mm).Morita T. Forward-looking remarks of the co-authors. She emphasized that patients with severe manifestations of periodontal disease (pocket depth 1 USD-4 mm) have a 2.2-fold increased risk of developing two or more components of the metabolic syndrome. Significant research has been conducted in Japan and other countries.

Periodontal disease and rheumatoid arthritis rheumatoid arthritis, as a systemic lesion of connective tissue, can be used as a predisposing factor for the occurrence and development, as well as a more serious process of pathological processes in periodontal tissues. In the presence of rheumatoid arthritis, significant microcirculation disorders occur in periodontal disease. On the contrary, chronic inflammatory lesions of the oral cavity can be triggers and supporting factors for the development of systemic diseases. Therefore, patients with severe periodontal tissue diseases are more likely to develop rheumatoid arthritis. At the same time, some researchers expressed doubts about the possibility of such a relationship. Inflammatory periodontal disease, i.e. bacterial infection, may also lead to increased serum levels. Nowak B. And Genco Rs. The relationship between the level of C-reactive protein and the severity of periodontal disease, in particular the relationship with the loss of alveolar attachment, has been established. The

mechanism of development of rheumatoid arthritis resonates with the pathogenesis of chronic periodontitis. So, in periodontal disease, the inflammatory process occurs due to the invasion of tissues by microbial endotoxins .

More and more scientists are talking about the autoimmune etiology of periodontal disease-a specific adaptive immune response to endogenous antigens. In the early stages of the development of rheumatoid arthritis as a systemic autoimmune inflammation, and in periodontal disease, an inflammatory response develops. Researcher Keenan D. F. and Marshall J. G. gingival Porphyromonas (BG), a microorganism, were isolated, immunological cross-reactivity was observed in 100% of cases. According to J. lydman. According to the co-author. (2012), patients with rheumatoid arthritis and periodontal disease have a higher susceptibility to pathogenic effects of PG, which leads to the secretion of antibodies containing cyclic peptide citrulline (ADCP). Pathogens can synthesize the enzyme peptidyl arginine deaminase, which is involved in the formation of citrulline peptides and creates the basis for the development of immune responses. Scientists noted that PG is the trigger for rheumatoid arthritis in people with a genetic predisposition. In the early stages of rheumatoid arthritis, the developing body plays an important pathogenetic role in the formation of autoimmune processes, which also determines the relationship between periodontal disease and rheumatoid arthritis. At this stage of periodontal disease, women's health and the weight of newborns, the interest of the medical community in "Sex Medicine" has increased. Men and women differ in epidemiology and progression of many diseases. Sex hormones regulate the function of cells involved in the immune response. Clinical observation of neutral dimorphism in diseases and conditions that seriously affect immune function is logically explained by differences in sex hormones. Women are characterized by increased antibody production compared to men, which corresponds to the advantages of autoimmune diseases such as systemic lupus erythematosus and rheumatoid arthritis, which are reflected in numerous scientific

studies (table). At an early age, an aggressive form of periodontal tissue pathology related to hormone levels in women may be detected. Therefore, changes in hormone levels during pregnancy can affect bacterial binding and inflammatory response. A connection between periodontitis and bacterial vaginosis and an increased risk of subsequent infertility in women under the age of 35 has been proven (Pretorius c.et Al.).

Endometriosis has a multifactorial etiology and is a possible cause of infertility, affects 6-10% of women of reproductive age. Since both endometriosis and periodontal disease are chronic inflammatory processes associated with altered immune responses, a causal relationship is proposed. Through this relationship, a changed inflammatory response to bacterial periodontal pathogens can lead to the development of endometriosis and a more active process. High levels of pro-inflammatory cytokines produced and released into the systemic circulation during microbial infections and inflammations in the oral cavity lead to muscle cell contraction and premature birth. Scientists discovered BG and FH. Nucleatum, in PG and A. Actinomycetemcometane in another study in amniotic fluid or placental samples of mothers with premature birth and gingivitis. The microbiome of the placenta and the mouth are very similar [11]. Inflammatory mediators caused by periodontal pathogens, transmitted by the circulatory system or produced by infected endometrial and placental tissues, play a vital role in the pathogenesis of premature birth in low-weight infants. Cytokines and immunoglobulins released during infection and aimed at oral microorganisms restrict the growth of pathogens on the one hand and enhance the inflammatory response on the other, leading to embryonic or fetal lesions . The effect of dental infections on the weight of newborns has been confirmed in several studies [58,62].

Some of the changes that occur in women during menopause cannot fail to affect the condition of the gum tissue. The role of osteoporosis is getting bigger and bigger, which can accelerate the resorption of alveolar bone in periodontal disease.

Estrogen regulates the proliferation of periodontal ligament cells and promotes the differentiation of osteoblasts. Estrogen deficiency causes bone resorption in response to cytokine-induced increased osteoclast formation. On the other hand, infections caused by periodontal pathogens can directly or indirectly contribute to a systemic inflammatory state, which activates osteoclasts. The primary role of vitamin D in regulating the differentiation and proliferation of mesenchymal cells before osteogenesis and the formation of bone tissue is documented in scientific papers [8]. It has been proven that postmenopausal women with vitamin D deficiency have a significant amount of loss of alveolar attachment, more missing teeth and active teeth, some teeth with destruction of the horn of bone tissue.

Conclusion: Therefore, the literature contains evidence of the relationship between chronic oral infections, cardiovascular and endocrine diseases, rheumatoid arthritis and other somatic cell diseases. There are biological mechanisms by which infection in the oral cavity can help initiate pathogenic mechanisms for the development of the pathology of many diseases that have not yet been fully studied. Various causes of physical failure prove that more in-depth examinations are needed for dental patients suffering from periodontal tissue diseases.

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